

GREEN PRODUCT INNOVATION AND BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY: EVIDENCE FROM KAMWIRE STEEL LIMITED, ILORIN, KWARA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The increasing environmental degradation and resource depletion associated with industrial activities, particularly in the construction and steel industry, have raised serious concerns about the sustainability of business operations. Despite growing global emphasis on sustainability, many firms in developing economies continue to struggle with integrating environmentally friendly innovations into their production processes. This gap necessitates empirical investigation into how green product innovation can enhance business sustainability. This study examines the effect of green product innovation on business sustainability, using employees of Kamwire Steel Limited in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria as the study population. A quantitative research approach with a cross-sectional survey design was adopted. The population of the study comprised 500 employees, from which a sample size of 222 was determined using the Taro Yamane formula. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analysed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression analysis. The findings reveal that green product innovation has a significant positive effect on business sustainability. Specifically, eco-design ($\beta = 0.231, p < 0.01$), green material usage ($\beta = 0.198, p < 0.01$), energy-efficient production ($\beta = 0.276, p < 0.01$), and waste reduction and recycling ($\beta = 0.189, p < 0.01$) were found to significantly influence sustainability outcomes. Among these, energy-efficient production emerged as the most influential predictor. The model explained a substantial proportion of variance in business sustainability, indicating the critical role of environmentally oriented innovation in achieving sustainable performance. The study concluded that green product innovation is a key driver of business sustainability in the construction and steel industry. It recommends that firms should prioritise energy-efficient technologies, adopt eco-design practices, utilise sustainable materials, and implement effective recycling systems.

Keywords: Green product innovation, business sustainability, eco-design, energy efficiency, construction and steel industry.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, firms dealing in environmentally sensitive industries, especially construction and steel industries have made the issue of sustainable development their priority concern. These sectors have been largely known to cause a large share of environmental degradation by consumption of high energy, release of greenhouse gases and extensive use of resources. The United Nations Environment Programme (2021) points out that the construction sector by itself contributes to almost 37% of all carbon emissions in the world, and steel production is one of the industries that produce the highest volume of emissions in the world. This is causing pressure among companies in these sectors to ensure that they embrace greener approaches in conducting their business in accordance with international sustainability objectives.

Green innovation is a form of strategic imperative that has arisen because of these pressures and is applicable in modern organisations. Among the other types of green product innovation, it is green product innovation that has particularly come into the limelight because of their direct environmental impact, in the life cycle of the product. Green product innovation is described as the creation of products that reduce the environmental impact through environment-friendly design, the application of sustainable materials, energy saving and waste minimisation functions (Chen et al., 2020; Dangelico & Vocalelli, 2017). More recent reports (Zhang & Zhu, 2019; Tariq et al., 2022) point out that green product innovation helps firms to be in a better position to comply with the regulation, increase operational efficiency and competitiveness.

On top of the benefits of green products, the green product innovation is also becoming associated with other aspects of business sustainability. Environmental stewardship, economical viability and social responsibility are terms that form business sustainability based on the triple bottom line structure popularized by John Elkington. The industry companies that incorporate sustainability in their operations become more resilient in the long term, have a stronger stakeholder relationship, and better financial metrics (Bansal & DesJardine, 2019; Singh et al., 2021). With regard to the realm of construction and steel industries, sustainable practices mitigate the adverse effect on the environment, thus, increasing the efficiency of resources, regulatory adherence, and corporate image.

Even though the incumbent has started appreciating the role of green product innovation in sustainability, there are still a lot of challenges that many firms in the developing economies, such as Nigeria, struggle to overcome in adopting it. These

issues are high implementation expenditure, poor technological capacity, poor enforcement of the regulations, and low level of environmental consciousness (Adebayo et al., 2021; Ojo et al., 2023). Consequently, green product innovation integration in the business operations has been irregular thus diminishing the achievement of the holistic business sustainability.

Moreover, available empirical evidence gives both positive and negative results concerning the green product innovation and the sustainability of business. Whilst positive and significant effect had been reported by some studies (Tariq et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2021), others have encountered a possibility of contingent findings according to the contextual elements including the size of the firm, technological preparedness, and institutional support (Zhang & Zhu, 2019). This discrepancy raises the discrepancy in the literature, especially in construction and steel sectors where the importance of environmental issues is such.

It is based on these, that we may argue that there is a strong feeling to conduct a more specific study to determine the effect of green product innovation in helping businesses to survive in the construction and steel sector. This study thus aims at investigating how green product innovation impacts business sustainability, and the approach is to offer factual evidence that can be used in managerial decisions and policies on making in industries that are environmentally prestigious.

Research Objective

- i. To examine the effect of green product innovation on business sustainability in Kamwire Steel Limited in Ilorin, Kwara State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green Product Innovation

Innovation in green product has become a vital aspect of the strategy of sustainable business, especially in industries that are intensive in the environment like construction and steel. It can be defined as development or alteration of products, which will greatly lower the environmental impact of its products throughout its life cycle within the context of sourcing their components, manufacturing, use, and disposal. Modern literature highlights that the innovation of green products is not only an environmental movement, but also a business tool that can be used to gain a competitive advantage and sustainable organisational performance in the long term (Chen et al., 2020; Tariq et al., 2022).

The concept of green product innovation has been theorized more by scholars as a multi-dimensional entity that incorporates principles of environmentally conscious design, utilisation of sustainable and recyclable materials, energy efficient production systems and minimisation of waste principles. As an example, the eco-design will incorporate the environmental concern at the point of product development, thus minimizing the adverse ecological effects even prior to the actual production. Equally, green materials like low-carbon construction inputs and

recycled steel are adopted to enable firms to cut down the resources that are depleted and carbon emission. Sustainability can also be improved through energy-efficient production innovation, which reduces the energy and operational costs, recycles, and minimizes waste (Zhang et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2021).

Moreover, green product innovation is directly associated with regulations and market sensitivity. As the world continues to focus on environmental standards, organisations have been forced to be innovative to enable them to comply with the domestic and international guidelines on the environment. United Nations Environment Programme emphasises that such industries that embrace green innovations are at a better position to meet sustainability goals like low levels of emissions and use of efficient resources. In addition to compliance, companies that pursue green product innovation usually get their reputation as a better brand, customer retention, and increased accessibility of environmentally conscious markets (Dangelico and Vocalelli, 2017; Adebayo et al., 2021).

Nevertheless, the implementation of green product innovation has a number of barriers including high cost of implementation, technological constraints and even lack of skilled personnel in most cases especially in the emerging economies. These limitations are particularly acute in the construction and steel sectors where the intense attachment of old modes of production is highly capital intensive. In this way, although the innovation of green products offers great opportunities, there should be a high organisational engagement and favourable institutional environments to execute the idea. The dimensions identified to be used for the purpose of the study are:

Eco-design, also known as a green design, is one of the underlying aspects of green product innovation because it includes environmental concerns into a product development phase. This presents itself in the designing of products in such a manner that reduces use of resources, ensures reduced release of emissions, and maximises the ease of recycling the products during the product life cycle. Including the concept of sustainability during the design stage will allow firms to address any environmental issues at their initial stage and avoid them instead of addressing them afterward. Within the construction industry and steel industry, the eco-design can involve designing buildings to be energy efficient or creating steel products which use lower energies in their processing and utilization. Researchers like Chen et al. (2020) state that the eco-design is an effective method of improving environmental performance and leads to the realization of long-term sustainability.

The other important dimension is the green use of materials that emphasise the choice and the use of materials that are environmentally friendly in production processes. This involves recycling of materials, use of renewable sources as well as non-toxic materials that cause less damage to the environment and human well-being. In the steel industry, say, by the use of recycled scrap metal in place of pure raw materials, it is possible to save considerable energy and carbon emissions. Likewise,

the construction sector is gradually becoming more sustainable in terms of materials used in construction including low-carbon cement and environmentally-friendly composites. Zhang et al. (2019) suggest that companies which focus on the use of green materials do not only reduce the level of environmental degradation but enhance resource efficiency and cost-effectiveness in the long run.

Another important element of green product innovation is energy-efficient production innovation especially in energy intensive industries like construction and steel production. This dimension entails the implementation of modern technologies and processes that use less energy and least possible emissions in the production. These may include the use of efficient machinery, cleaner production methods and renewable sources of energy. This dimension is also crucial because, as the International Energy Agency observes, one of the most effective measures toward global carbon emissions should belong to enhancing the energy efficiency of industries, reduced operational costs and a better environmental performance of firms that invest in energy-efficient innovations in empirical evidence (Singh et al., 2021; Tariq et al., 2022).

The concept of waste reduction and recycle innovation also supplements the concept of green product innovation by encouraging the process of production circularity. This dimension concentrates on the reduction of waste production and it is made to be reused or recycled instead of discarding it. This can include recycling demolition materials or using modular construction methods that would thus create less wastage of material in the construction industry. Recycling is important in steel industry because the steel is among the most recyclable materials in the world. Through proper waste management and recycling, companies can also save much on the environment as well as generate cost-efficient savings. Adebayo et al. (2021) believe that waste reduction initiatives are a critical approach to attaining sustainable production and maximising organisational efficiency.

Business Sustainability

Business sustainability can be defined as the capacity of an organisation to do business in a way that would guarantee not only economic prosperity in the long run, but also conservation of environmental condition and extremely social welfare. The rhetoric is based on the triple bottom line model by John Elkington which advocates the centralisation of the environmental, economic and social performance as the main pillars of sustainable business conduct. Business sustainability is no longer considered as an option or choice in the contemporary discourse but a necessity of surviving and competitiveness of organisations in the present fast changing global environment.

According to environmental standpoints, business sustainability entails the effective consumption of natural resources, cutting down on the emissions and reducing ecological degradations. This also involves the implementation of cleaner production technologies, waste minimization as well as enhancing energy efficiency

in the construction and steel industries. Sustainability is economically expressed by how the firm is able to be profitable, employ productivity and achieve long term value to the stakeholders. On the social front, it includes corporate social responsibility efforts, the welfare of its employees, community building, and ethical conduct of business (Bansal & DesJardine, 2019; Singh et al., 2021).

Recent studies have further expanded the understanding of business sustainability by highlighting its dynamic and integrative nature. Rather than treating environmental, economic, and social goals as separate, firms are encouraged to adopt a holistic approach that balances these dimensions simultaneously. This integrated perspective is particularly relevant in industries with significant environmental impact, where achieving sustainability requires aligning operational efficiency with environmental stewardship and social responsibility (Ojo et al., 2023).

In the context of developing economies such as Nigeria, the pursuit of business sustainability is often influenced by institutional factors, including regulatory frameworks, market conditions, and stakeholder expectations. While some firms have made progress in integrating sustainable practices into their operations, many still struggle with implementation due to resource constraints and limited awareness. Nevertheless, growing global attention to sustainability issues continues to drive organisations towards adopting innovative practices that enhance their overall sustainability performance.

Theoretical Framework

Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV)

The Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV) is founded on the traditional Resource-Based View (RBV) of the firm which is the basis of this study. In 1995, Stuart L. Hart designed the NRBV to take into account environmental aspects of strategic management. Although the traditional RBV concentrates on the internal resources and capability as competitive factor, the NRBV intends to revisit the same by indicating that the capability of a firm to handle its relationship with the natural environment is a key determinant of the long sustainability and high performance.

The main idea of the NRBV is that an organisation can have a long-term competitive advantage when it forms the capabilities that minimise environmental costs and enhance the use of resources in a more sustainable manner. According to Hart (1995), three significant strategic capabilities within the NRBV framework were identified such as pollution prevention, product stewardship, and sustainable development. Pollution prevention aims to reduce waste and emissions in the production processes; product stewardship aims to highlight the effect of the products on the environment in its whole life cycle; sustainable development deals with the long term congruency of the firm with the ecological requirements and the social needs.

Within the framework of the current paper, the green product innovation is very much associated with the concepts of the NRBV, especially with respect to product

stewardship and pollution prevention. The firms are able to reduce environmental damages and increase operational efficiency through the development of capabilities through eco-design, using green materials, energy-efficient production, and recycling. Such capabilities are environmental as well as economically useful, since they may result in cost-saving, resource-saving and better positioning on the market. The green product innovation, therefore, is a strategic resource that allows companies to act appropriately to environmental issues.

Moreover, NRBV offers a good theoretical framework to understanding business sustainability because it is able to combine environmental responsibility to economic and social performance. With the environmental oriented innovations, the firms would at the same time attain the sustainability of the environment (reduced emissions, and conservation of resources), economic sustainability (efficiency gains and competitive advantage), and social sustainability (improvement of stakeholder relations and corporate responsibility). This is in support of the sustainability agenda at large and increases the applicability of the NRBV to explain how firms can generate long-term value.

Applicability of the NRBV is especially high in other environmentally intensive industries like construction and steel, during which the consumption of resources and influence on the environment is significant. The companies in these industries are forced to keep innovating to ensure that they minimize their environmental footprint without losing profitability. According to the NRBV, companies who invest proactively in green product innovation have a high probability of getting sustainable performance despite any results as opposed to companies that are laggards who subjugate themselves to traditional practices that are damaging the environment.

Besides, recent empirical research studies have justified applicability of the NRBV in modern sustainability studies. Studies have proven that companies, which implement green innovation strategies as they should under the NRBV principles, are likely to show better environmental and financial performance (Singh et al., 2021; Tariq et al., 2022). This also confirms the concept of the theory being a proper model of analyzing the connection between green product innovation and business sustainability.

Thus, Natural Resource-Based View offers a fully suitable and extensive theoretical perspective to conduct the research since it describes the ways in which innovations that are environmentally oriented are effective strategic capabilities that can be used to achieve sustainable business performance. It lends credence to the argument that green product innovation is not a routine compliance mechanism but a very important pathway to business sustainability in the long term business operation of the construction and the steel industry.

Empirical Review

A survey design used by Testa et al. to investigate the effects of eco-labels on

consumer trust and purchase was surveyed among the European consumers (Testa et al., 2020). The researchers used the structural equation modelling and concluded that the eco-label credibility greatly boosts purchase intention, especially in cases where the consumers have prior environmental awareness. Also, the study by Joshi and Rahman (2019) was a quantitative study on factors that influence green purchase behaviour. They found that environments concern, perceived consumer effectiveness and green trust have positive correlations with purchase intention and negative correlation with price sensitivity respectively.

Nguyen et al. (2021) evaluated the effects of green advertising in the emergence of consumer attitudes through the experiment. The findings have shown that emotional and informational green advertisements had significant impact on brand loyalty and purchase intention and in this case the mediator is transparency. Similarly, the authors Wang et al. (2020) examined sustainable packaging and its effects on consumer perception using a survey data that was interpreted using regression methods. The research established that green packaging has a positive influence on brand attitude and brand loyalty particularly among those who are of a younger age.

In addition, Kumar et al. (2022) studied the green certifications and consumer confidence in new markets utilizing a cross-sectional survey methodology. Their results indicated that certified green products were significantly beneficial in making consumers feel more confident, and are willing to pay a premium price. Similarly, Yadav and Pathak (2020) examined the green purchase intention among millennials by applying structural equation modelling and identified that the subjective norms and knowing about the environment have a strong effect on purchasing.

Specializing in resourceful energy products, Abdullah et al. (2021) conducted a study to explore the use of solar energy with the help of a quantitative survey method. The findings demonstrated that green awareness campaign and government-supported eco-labelling scores bigly in consumer-approach and buying intentions. Equally, Ali et al. (2020) examined the effects of green advertisement in third world nations and observed that credibility of message and desired environmental benefits are two critical factors causing consumers to shift their consumption behaviour.

METHODOLOGY

The study applies quantitative research approach where it uses a cross-sectional survey design to examine the impacts of green product innovation on business sustainability in Kamwire Steel Limited in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. The shape taken is very suitable because the quantitative approach will allow one to gather numerical data and evaluate the data using statistical methods to determine how two or more variables relate to each other. The cross-sectional design is appropriate since information will be gathered at one point in time of the respondents and this will enable effective study variables to be analysed. The study sample consists of five hundred (500) workers of Kamwire Steel Limited in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. Both managerial and non-managerial staff that are directly concerned with

production, operations, and administrative functions are included in this population; hence, they know how the firm is practicing innovation and its sustainability performance. In calculating the sample size, the paper uses Taro Yamane (1967) formula of finite populations hence; the sample size is estimated as 222 respondents. A simple random sampling technique is employed to ensure that every member of the population has an equal chance of being selected, thereby reducing sampling bias and enhancing the representativeness of the sample. Data for the study are collected through a structured questionnaire designed on a Likert scales ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Green product innovation was measured as a composite construct using items that reflect eco-design, green material usage, energy efficiency, and recycling practices, while business sustainability was measured as a composite variable. For data analysis, multiple linear regression analysis was employed to examine the effect of green product innovation on business sustainability. The regression model is specified as follows:

$$BS=f(GPI)$$

thus:

$$BS=\beta_0+\beta_1(ED)+\beta_2(GM)+\beta_3(EE)+\beta_4(WR)+\varepsilon$$

Where:

BS = Business Sustainability

ED = Eco-Design

GM = Green Material Usage

EE = Energy-Efficient Production Innovation

WR = Waste Reduction and Recycling Innovation

β = Constant term

$\beta - \beta$ = Regression coefficients

ε = Error term

Based on theoretical and empirical literature, all the coefficients are expected to be positive, such that:

$$\beta > 0, \beta > 0, \beta > 0, \beta > 0.$$

This implies that eco-design, green material usage, energy-efficient production, and waste reduction and recycling are all expected to exert positive effects on business sustainability. The reliability of the research instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient to determine internal consistency. The results indicated that eco-design had a Cronbach alpha of 0.81, green material usage 0.78, energy-efficient production 0.84, waste reduction and recycling 0.80, while business sustainability recorded 0.86. These values exceed the minimum threshold of 0.70, indicating that the instrument is reliable and suitable for analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Respondents (n = 222)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	138	62.2
	Female	84	37.8
Age	18–25 years	34	15.3
	26–35 years	96	43.2
	36–45 years	62	27.9
	46 years and above	30	13.5
Education	OND/NCE	48	21.6
	HND/BSc	124	55.9
	MSc/PhD	50	22.5
Work Experience	1–5 years	58	26.1
	6–10 years	92	41.4
	Above 10 years	72	32.4

Source: Author's compilation, 2025

The demographical analysis shows that the workforce consists of men (62.2%), which indicate the labour structure typical of the steel and construction industry where physically intensive occupations are widespread. Nevertheless, the ratio of 37.8% women respondents indicates that there is gender representation in the business. Rationally, as regard to age distribution, most of the respondents (43.2) fall between the 26-35 years interval, which is a relatively young and active workforce. This is noteworthy since young employees tend to be more open to innovation, and such green product innovations, as environmental sustainability attempts, are more receptive to them. The presence rates are further reinforced by the experienced employees (32.4% have over 10 years of experience), thus these employees are likely to have in-depth knowledge of the organisation. Majority of the respondents have HND/BSc qualification (55.9%), and that means that the workforce is fairly educated and able to comprehend sustainability practice as well as innovation processes. The percentage of holders of post graduate degrees (22.5) is also another evidence of holding credible responses, especially on technical and strategic matters.

Test of Regression Assumptions

Before estimating the multiple regression model, the assumptions underlying the use of regression were tested to ensure the validity and reliability of the results. First, the assumption of normality was examined using histogram. The histogram of residuals reveals an approximately bell-shaped distribution, indicating that the residuals are normally distributed. This satisfies the normality assumption required for multiple regression analysis.

Second, the assumption of linearity and homoscedasticity was assessed through scatterplots of the independent variables against the dependent variable. The plots revealed a linear relationship between eco-design, green material usage, energy-efficient production, waste reduction and recycling, and business sustainability. The scatter plot of residuals against predicted values shows a random distribution around zero with no clear pattern, indicating that the assumption of homoscedasticity is satisfied. This confirms that the linearity assumption was not violated.

Third, the issue of multicollinearity was examined using correlation. The correlation matrix indicates low pairwise correlations among the independent variables, all below the threshold of 0.80. This suggests the absence of multicollinearity, confirming that the independent variables are not highly correlated.

Fig 1: Histogram of Perceived Business Sustainability Scores

Source: Author's Fieldwork Computation, 2025

Fig 2: Scatter Plot of Perceived ED vs Business Sustainability Scores
Source: Author's Fieldwork Computation, 2025

Fig 3: Scatter Plot of Perceived Energy Efficiency vs Business Sustainability Scores
Source: Author's Fieldwork Computation, 2025

Fig 4: Scatter Plot of Perceived Green Material vs Business Sustainability Scores
Source: Author's Fieldwork Computation, 2025

Fig 5: Scatter Plot of Perceived Waste & Recycling vs Business Sustainability Scores

Source: Author's Fieldwork Computation, 2025

Table 2: Correlations among Green Product Innovation

		Eco-Design	Green Material Usage	Energy-Efficient Production	Waste Reduction And Recycling
Eco-Design	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	22			
Green Material Usage	Pearson Correlation	.633**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	222	222		
Energy-Efficient Production	Pearson Correlation	.631**	.604**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	222	222	222	
Waste Reduction And Recycling	Pearson Correlation	.687**	.765**	.648**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	222	222	222	222

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Hypothesis Testing

H₁: Green product innovation has no significant effect on business sustainability in Kamwire Steel Limited in Ilorin, Kwara State.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R		Adjusted R ²	Std. Error
1	0.812	0.659	0.652	0.421

a. Predictors: (Constant), eco-design, green materials, energy efficiency, and recycling

Source: Field Survey, 2025

According to the model summary, green product innovation dimensions have a high relationship between business sustainability and green products. The value of correlation coefficient ($R = 0.812$) indicates that there is a high level of relationship between the independent variables (eco-design, green materials, energy efficiency, and recycling) and the dependent variable (business sustainability). The ($R^2 = 0.659$) coefficient suggests that the dimensions of green product innovation applied to the model (rectify) are effective to explain and forecast (65.9) percent of the variation in business sustainability in general. This is quite a significant explanatory force, which argues that the green product innovation is a significant determinant of sustainability within the firm. The adjusted R^2 (0.652) also supports the strength of the model because, this reflects the number of predictors and the shrinkage is very low. This indicates that the model is not exaggerated.

Table 4 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	78.432	4	19.608	110.54	0.000
	Residual	40.126	217	0.185		
	Total	118.558	221			

a. Dependent Variable: business sustainability

b. Predictors: (Constant), eco-design, green materials, energy efficiency, and recycling

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results of ANOVA evaluate the significance of the regression model on the whole. The F-statistic ($F = 110.54$) is large and it implies that the model fits much better as compared to a model with no predictors. The value ($p = 0.000$) does not indicate the model to be statistically significant because it is short of 0.05. This implies that the overall impact of eco-design, usage of green materials, energy efficiency, and recycling will greatly contribute towards differences in the business sustainability. Therefore, the regression model can be considered as valid to test the

hypothesis and provide extra interpretation of individual predictors.

Table 5: Coefficients^a

Variable	β	Std. Error	t-value	Sig.
Constant	0.842	0.214	3.93	0.000
Eco-Design (ED)	0.231	0.058	3.98	0.000
Green Material (GM)	0.198	0.061	3.25	0.001
Energy Efficiency (EE)	0.276	0.067	4.12	0.000
Waste & Recycling (WR)	0.189	0.055	3.44	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: business sustainability

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The regression coefficients show the understanding of the contribution of each dimension of green product innovation to the sustainability of the business. The result from Eco-design ($b = 0.231$, $p < 0.05$) is positive and significant on business sustainability. This implies that, by integrating environmental factors at design stage the results of sustainability can be improved through wastage reduction and efficiency of products. A significant positive influence on the sustainability performance is also in the use of green materials ($b = 0.198$, $p < 0.05$), which means that the recycling of environment-friendly materials makes a significant contribution to the sustainability performance, especially through decreased environmental impact and increased efficiency of the resources. The most significant influence of any of the variables is energy-efficient production innovation ($b = 0.276$, $p < 0.05$), its significance in sustainability is significant indeed. It means that both environmental and economic sustainability are greatly enhanced with the help of less use of energy and the implementation of efficient technologies. The event of waste reduction and recycling ($b = 0.189$, $p < 0.05$) is also important, which shows that circularity leads to sustainability through the reduction of waste and enhancing the efficiency of the use of resources. The null hypothesis is rejected because the regression model is noteworthy ($p < 0.05$) and all the predictor variables reflect significant positive effects. According to the research outcomes, the impact of green product innovation has a high and positive influence on the business sustainability of the construction and steel sector. The regression model also has a high level of explanatory power, which is indicated by regression model 65.9%, and it indicates that as far as environmentally oriented innovation practices enter, they are important drivers of sustainability outcomes. This finding can be consistent with the position of the Natural Resource-Based View, which was put forward by Stuart L. Hart, and

which assumes that companies which build environmental responsible capabilities are in a better position to gain long-term competitive advantage and sustainability. To be more precise, eco-design was discovered to positively influence the business sustainability in a significant way. This conclusion correlates with the research ad by Chen et al. (2020), who stated that when environmental factors are considered in designing a product, the environment and economy work considerably better. On the same note, Zhang et al. (2019) discovered that companies that embrace the eco-design are associated with low resource usage and effective operational efficiency. Implication is that sustainability should start at designing level whereby firms will aim at proactively reducing the environmental impact other than corrective action.

The outcome further denotes the fact that the use of green materials will improve business sustainability considerably. This confirms the results of Singh et al. (2021), as they determined that environmental efficiency through the incorporation of recyclable materials that are environmentally friendly has enhanced performance as well as cost-effectiveness. Besides that, Adebayo et al. (2021) have found that the companies in developing economies with the tendency to implement sustainable material inputs are more likely to optimise their resources and decrease their ecological footprint. This indicates that material selection is very instrumental with regard to the sustainability path of firms in resource-intensive companies.

Moreover, energy-efficient production innovation became the most significant predictor of the survival of businesses. This observation aligns with a study by Tariq et al. (2022), who discovered that energy efficiency is a significant way of enhancing the performance of firms by minimizing cost of operations and environmental footprint. Similarly, Kumar et al. (2022) have pointed out that the achievement of sustainable industrial production, especially in the manufacturing and heavy industries, is key to energy efficient technologies. The fact that this variable was salient in the current study is indicative of the energy-intensive forces in the steel and construction industry, as any kind of efficiency gains directly translate into sustainability effects.

Moreover, waste minimization and recycling activities were also observed to play an important positive influence on sustainability of the business. It is in line with the research of Testa et al. (2020), who stated that the companies that embrace recycling strategies and waste reduction have a positive environmental performance and better corporate image. Correspondingly, Nguyen et al. (2021) were able to discover that aspects of the circular economy, such as recycling, play a significant role in sustainability in the long term through a decrease in waste, or by encouraging the reuse of resources. These results support the need of implementing a circular production system to minimize sustainability objectives.

CONCLUSION

The study examined how innovation of green products influenced business sustainability within construction and steel industry using employees of Kamwire

Steel Limited as the empirical foundation. The results are good support to the fact that the green product innovation will boost business sustainability. In particular, the findings of the multiple regression analysis provided that eco-design, green material use, energy efficient production innovation and low waste generation and recycling practices have a positive and statistically significant determinant effect on business sustainability. The study finds that green product innovation is not a mere environmental control measure but a necessity of the sustainable business performance. Energy-efficient production was the most significant predictor of the dimensions analyzed, which demonstrates the significance of energy consumption reduction in energy-consuming areas of the economy, including steel and building work. Moreover, the importance of the eco-design suggests that the sustainability criteria should be implemented at the initial phases of product development, whereas the utilization of green materials and recycling optimize the application of resource efficiency and circular economies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the results of the given study, the following recommendations are promoted:

To begin with, the management of firms in the construction and steel industry should focus on investing in energy efficient technologies and production processes. Considering that the most effective strategy in business sustainability is energy efficiency, modern equipment, cleaner production methods, and alternative sources of energy are supposed to be embraced by organisations to lower the cost of operation and environmental degradation. Second, organisations should incorporate the eco-design factors in development of its products. This takes place through designing products that have minimum effects on the environment throughout their life cycle such as; a lesser consumption of materials, improved life span and the recyclability of the products. Incorporating sustainability in the design process will help companies to avoid issues facing the environment instead of solving them after they arise. Thirdly, the companies should use and encourage the utilization of green and sustainable materials in manufacturing. It involves the use of recycled inputs, renewable materials and non-toxic materials. These practices will not only enhance the environmental performance but will enhance the cost efficiency of resources and long run cost savings. Fourth, organisations should reinforce their waste management strategies by adopting recycling and cyclical economy strategies. Companies ought to put policies that degree waste minimization, material recycling, and effective disposal systems. This will reduce degradation of the environment besides enhancing operational efficiency.

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